

Safe Mothers in Low-income Emergency Settings (SMiLES): Local Community Research Findings

Using “Lay Epidemiology” to evaluate the scope of training traditional birth attendants in Cameroon

In memory of Dr. Martina Lukong Baye, who passed away in July 2022.

“You are on the right path. Research first. Understand the reasons.”

These were the guiding words of the former Coordinator of the National Multi-sector Programme to Combat Maternal, Newborn and Child Mortality, in Cameroon, and early advisor and supporter of the SMiLES project. Dr Baye shaped the project focus on community engagement and expert-informed training.

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“It has been such an honour partnering with Public Health Pathways on the SMiLES Project. I sincerely thank the entire team for their selfless contributions and the opportunity to collaborate on such important work, which greatly affects the lives of women and, worst of all, in conflict settings.

Thank you to the Public Health Pathways team, for touching Cameroonian women's lives and bringing us in contact with several partners from your community in the UK and beyond.

Now we've laid the groundwork; we hope it will be easier to proceed from here as we call on partners interested in working in Maternal Mortality in Cameroon to the Welisane Foundation team in making SMiLES a reality.”

Mokwe Welisane Nkeng

“Welisane and her colleagues listened to the voices of those living in the South West. They allowed the Public Health Pathways team access to develop an understanding through carefully processing insights that the people in Meanja, Muyaka, and Ekona volunteered.

We hope the SMiLES report brings an appreciation of the innovation occurring in communities and the profound potential in investing in grassroots initiatives to strengthen the resilience of healthcare systems.”

Theo Richardson-Gool

Safe Mothers in Low-income Emergency Settings (SMiLES): Local Community Research Findings

Using “Lay Epidemiology” to evaluate the scope of training traditional birth attendants in South West Cameroon

Abstract

This study aimed to gain a deeper understanding of the challenges in accessing maternal healthcare services faced by communities in South West Cameroon, Muyuka Health District. The results demonstrate that the community supports the training of traditional birth attendants (“TBAs”) in midwifery to meet the urgent needs of mothers and new-borns. The ongoing Anglophone Crisis within Cameroon has aggravated financial constraints, which are the primary reason for delays in decision-making in medical care. The conflict has directly impacted the ability of mothers to receive care, resulting in instances of giving birth in the “bush” without technical medical assistance, which has led to complications during pregnancy and birth. The survey results aligned with the Three Delays Model, which highlights the delay in making a decision, reaching a health facility, and receiving care in maternal health.

Reaching a health facility was a challenge for many respondents, with 25 (55.5%) citing cost, distance, or lack of equipment/resources as reasons for dissatisfaction with health services. The closure of 9 out of 10 health facilities has resulted in limited access to health services in the region (Dr Eko, 2023). Malaria was identified as a significant medical challenge, with infectious diseases threatening maternal, foetal, and infant health. In the Muyuka Health District, social challenges include the economic toll of the conflict, leading to job loss, poverty, and decreased access to healthcare. Structural challenges include the closure of health facilities, safety concerns, and a lack of staff and resources.

Before conducting this “lay epidemiology” study, the research hypothesis was that the community requires these findings to support a bridge to healthcare access that TBAs can provide. This includes understanding the lack of confidence and trust in healthcare systems due to the lack of available, accessible, and affordable maternal healthcare services hugely damaged by the conflict. The study provides insights into community concerns and the best way to disseminate health information within the community, with a mix of digital and analogue methods preferred. The analysis highlights the importance of addressing medical, social, and structural challenges in South West Cameroon, which is demonstrated through using the Three Delays Model in order to understand the barriers to accessing healthcare. The findings corroborate previous studies ([Ambe et al., 2020](#); [Achidi et al., 2009](#); [Gabriel et al., 2020](#); [Egbe et al., 2018](#)) in Cameroon that identified several factors affecting maternal mortality, including lack of trust, poverty, low levels of antenatal care, lack of knowledge, and the need for targeted interventions.

This research will be used to plan an intervention that addresses the challenges faced by communities in accessing maternal healthcare services in South West Cameroon through training TBAs in midwifery. By identifying the key factors affecting access to healthcare, the study provides valuable insights into how to improve the delivery of healthcare services in the region and reduce maternal mortality. The results of this study can inform the development of targeted interventions that address the medical, social, and structural challenges faced by communities in the region and provide a roadmap for improving access to quality maternal healthcare services.

1. Introduction to the Project Research

The Welisane Foundation (a Cameroon-based NGO) and Public Health Pathways (a UK-based NGO) have partnered to study and reduce maternal mortality in South West Cameroon. The partnership aims to develop a locally led project that benefits from local knowledge systems and healthcare expertise. The aim is to train traditional birth attendants (TBAs) in midwifery. Before starting the project, it was essential to obtain input from the local community to ensure the intervention is genuinely inclusive.

The Ashworth Charitable Trust provided a grant for the research phase of the SMiLES project. The study is locally led and locally informed, and the hypothesis is that TBAs require further training with professional medical practitioners to build on

existing local capacity, knowledge systems, connections, and trust within the community. The SMILES project is the first in the South West region that aims to empower TBAs and reduce maternal mortality while building community resilience.

1.1 The Anglophone Crisis

Cameroon continues to face the postcolonial challenge of consolidating a single national identity, as there are sustained conflicts between its Anglophone and Francophone citizens. When the Republic of Cameroon acquired full independence in 1960, the north-western and south-western regions were under the merged British colonial influence with Nigeria (Agwanda *et al.*, 2020). Since October 2016, Cameroon's Anglophone North West and South West regions have faced a crisis, as groups fight either to return to the federal government system or for the independence of the English regions to form a nation called Ambazonia (Nganji and Cockburn, 2018). This ongoing conflict has had a significant impact on maternal health in the country, with many health facilities in the affected regions becoming inaccessible due to violence and insecurity. This has left many women without access to essential maternal health services, and hence, increased the risk of maternal mortality and morbidity. The latest United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) Situation Report [December 7, 2022] shows that at least 885,211 people need adequate, dignified shelter. Presently, there are 420,000 returnees (former internally displaced persons) and refugees. At the same time, attacks on healthcare systems continue to affect the availability of healthcare services. One incident was reported in the Muyuka health district in the South West, where two health workers were kidnapped and released only two days later (OCHA, 2022).

1.2 Health Indicators

The Cameroon Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) of 2018 found that modern family planning is more prevalent and most births are attended at health facilities in urban areas, but the data do not reflect the reality in rural areas. These areas have a higher fertility rate and indicators have been negatively impacted by the Anglophone crisis. A study found the maternal mortality rate at 240 per 100,000 live births in Mutengene with the main causes being haemorrhage, prolonged labour, malaria, anaemia, abortion, sepsis, and HIV/AIDS (Ambe *et al.*, 2020). Data also indicate high rates of malaria and teenage pregnancy in Tiko Health District (Achidi *et al.*, 2009; Gabriel *et al.*, 2020). The prevalence of gestational diabetes was 20.5% in Limbe and it was associated with advanced maternal age, excess weight, a past history of stillbirth, and macrosomia. The findings show the need for targeted interventions to prevent poor obstetrical outcomes (Egbe *et al.*, 2018).

1.3 Other health interventions South West Cameroon

Three previous maternal health interventions that have been implemented in the South West include:

- An intervention in the Tiko CDC plantation camp, which combined health education, strengthening facilities, and the distribution of contraceptives. The outcomes are to be measured in the 3rd, 6th and 9th months after the baseline, and they include contraceptive knowledge, perception, practise, maternal and infant morbi-mortality. The results are yet to be published (Emeh *et al.*, 2021).
- A full course of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria during pregnancy, which has been adopted to control malaria's impact on maternal health. In the Muyuka Health District, adherence to full course treatment was low (32%), but it reduced the odds of malaria during pregnancy and improved neonatal birth weight and gestational age (Yoah *et al.*, 2018).
- Another health strategy to control malaria, which is the use of mosquito bed nets. Fru *et al.*, (2021) identified the following reasons for the irregular use of mosquito bed nets in the Tiko Health District: “it gives heat” (21.1%), forgetfulness (6.5%), use of fan (2.8%), difficulty to install (2.4%), and use of mosquito repellent (2.2%).

These examples of health interventions in South West Cameroon demonstrate the importance of addressing the various factors that impact maternal health. Similarly, the SMILES project aims to address multiple barriers to maternal health by providing midwifery training to TBAs, distributing safe delivery kits, and building community resilience. By taking a comprehensive approach to maternal health, the project aims to reduce maternal and infant mortality in the region.

2. Project background

Stakeholder interviews were conducted between 2021 and 2022 with Dr Martina Baye, at the time, Coordinator for the National Multisector Program to Combat Maternal, Newborn and Child Mortality in Cameroon; Dr Arif Alibhai, President and

CEO of the non-profit agency HEAL International; Marc Serna, Programme Director for Reachout Cameroon; and Dr Alain Eko, at the time, Medical Officer for the UNDP and ex-Medical Officer for the Ministry of Health in Cameroon.

All stakeholders emphasised the importance of community engagement and the utilisation of local resources to address maternal health challenges in rural areas. Dr. Baye recommended using data to identify prevalent health problems and engaging with communities to understand their specific challenges and solutions. Dr. Alibhai emphasised the need to prioritise monitoring and evaluation of long-term interventions and establishing a local advisory group.

Figure 1. Martina Lukong Baye (left) with the first members of the SMiLES project team.

Marc Serna highlighted the limited access to healthcare facilities and shortage of trained practitioners in the Muyuka region, and suggested implementing an early alert system where nurses visit communities and integrate a sustainable livelihoods approach that comprises factoring in human, social, natural, physical, and financial capital (Serrat, O. 2017). Additionally, Dr. Eko proposed training TBAs to support the community in maternal health. Overall, the stakeholders emphasised the need for safety due to the ongoing conflict and for working within existing systems to avoid duplication of efforts. These insights align with the goals of the SMiLES project to improve maternal health outcomes in the affected regions by working closely with communities and local health authorities.

3. Methodology

Lay epidemiology

This is a term used to describe the use of community-based knowledge and experiences in the field of public health. It involves the active participation of communities in the collection, analysis, and use of data related to health and illness. The goal of lay epidemiology is to genuinely involve communities and give them a voice in shaping their own health and wellbeing. This approach recognizes that communities often have unique perspectives and insights into the health challenges they face, which can be valuable in informing public health policies and programs (Davey Smith., et al, 1993; Lewin S A, 2005)

Three Delays Model

The Three Delays Model is a pertinent framework validated to identify access barriers to maternal care in low and middle-income countries by considering the delay to take a decision, reach a health facility, and receive care. It aids in describing the different levels that interact: household, community, and health system (Actis Danna *et al.*, 2020; Shah., et al, 2020;

Thaddeus & Maine, 1994). To apply the Three Delays Model, a community-led survey was conducted to identify factors contributing to delays in maternal healthcare utilisation in South West Cameroon.

Patient and public involvement

Patients or the public were involved locally in the design, conduct, and reporting plans of the research.

Research Design

The purpose of this study was to assess the community's needs and support for TBAs to receive midwifery training. A mixed methods approach was used to test the hypothesis that TBAs would benefit from training and that the community would support it. The survey design was co-developed by the Public Health Pathways global team; the Welisane Foundation in Cameroon; Dr Alain Eko; and Dr Abass Alhassan, a lead lecturer in Embryology/Histology at the University of Central Lancaster. The survey consisted of both open-ended and closed-ended questions, with a focus on community involvement.

Data Collection

The field team conducted 50 face-to-face interviews in April 2022 in five locations in South West Cameroon (Muyuka, Meanja, Ekona, Bafia, and Malende). The sample was diverse and respondents were required to provide informed consent and live in one of the five areas. The team aimed to interview respondents from different socioeconomic backgrounds, locations, and age groups. The responses were transcribed, translated, and entered into a digital database.

Data Analysis

The collected data was organised and analysed using descriptive statistical analysis. The survey comprised 29 questions: 19 concerned experiences and 10 concerned demographics. Thirty eight valid responses were received, which inform this report, focusing on Meanja, Muyaka, and Ekona (MME) due to limited responses from Bafia and Malende. A number of respondents did not provide responses for all of the questions asked, as some of the questions did not apply to the respondent or they chose not to answer the question. The report clarifies how many responses each respective analysis received for calculating results. As a small number of respondents gave multiple insights to some questions, this report shows the percentages as a proportion based on the total insights given per question asked.

Respondents

Of the 38 respondents, 17 (45%) were from Ekona, 15 (39%) from Meanja, and 6 (16%) from Muyuka. The ages ranged from 19 to 44 years old (mean age: 29 years), with 29 (76%) women and 9 (24%) men interviewed. The majority of respondents (n = 20, 55%) were married, and the average number of children per family was 2.75.

Languages spoken

Of the 33 respondents who provided information on languages spoken, 13 (40%) spoke English, 11 (33%) spoke Pidgin English, and 10 (29%) spoke a local language, dialect, or mother tongue. 11 (33%) of the respondents spoke more than one language.

Religion

Of the 34 respondents who provided information on religion, 18 (53%) were Christian (excluding Catholics and Presbyterians), 11 (32%) Catholic, 4 (12%) Presbyterian, and 1 (3%) Muslim. This diversity may impact cultural beliefs and practices surrounding maternal health and birth.

Employment and income

Of the 27 respondents who identified their occupations, 7 (25%) were farmers, 5 (19%) were housewives, and 5 (19%) were businesspeople. Other occupations included 2 (7%) students, 2 (7%) traders, 2 (7%) teachers, 1 (4%) seamstresses, 1 (4%) hunters, 1 (4%) healthcare workers/TBAs, and 1 (4%) hairdressers. Many of the respondents who identified as businesspeople were likely farmers (Dr Eko, 2023). Further, of the 11 respondents who provided their annual income, 7 (64%) earned between 25,000 to 50,000 Coopération financière en Afrique centrale (“FCA”) (\$8 to \$17), with the remaining 4 (36%) earning more. Unemployment rates may be higher, and income rates may be lower, than those observed in the data (Dr Eko, 2023). Most people before the conflict earned less than 25,000 FCA and were dependent on incomes from the local plantation, which employed the majority of local farmers, earning between 15,000 and 25,000 FCA (Dr Eko, 2023). Moreover, this could reflect an element of social desirability bias where respondents present more socially acceptable answers than their true behaviours (Bispo Júnior, 2022) as the respondents interviewed may feel pride and not wish to disclose a status of unemployment.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical standards by providing informed consent, anonymising data, and providing training on ethical considerations for field workers. Guidelines for conducting interviews and explaining consent forms followed United Nations

Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (UN OCHA) and United Nations World Health Organisation (UN WHO) standards.

4. Fieldwork Results

4.1 Health Priorities

The survey showed that most health priorities identified by the community are preventable and manageable diseases and illnesses. Many respondents identified multiple health priorities; 89 different insights were received from 38 respondents. 33 (36.5%) specifically mentioned malaria, 19 (21%) highlighted other infectious diseases [comprising typhoid and cholera], 11 (12%) identified non-communicable diseases [comprising diabetes and breast cancer], 10 (11%) highlighted ‘headaches, coughs, fever, and diarrhoea’, 9 (10%) mentioned Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs) and HIV/AIDs [accounted for separately from ‘other infectious diseases’ as STDs], and 3 (3.5%) mentioned skin diseases and rashes. The other seven health priorities highlighted by those surveyed are as follows: 1 (1%) ‘road traffic accidents’, 1 (1%), ‘excess labour’, 1 (1%) ‘poverty’, 1 (1%) ‘substance abuse’, 1 (1%) ‘water’ [unclear whether this relates to unclean water or poor access to water], and 1 (1%) ‘violence’.

“I witnessed many of my friends lose their lives while trying to give birth in the bushes; some bled, and there was nothing to help stop or replace the blood.”

Respondents experiences of complications that occurred during childbirth in the bush.

4.2 Maternal Health Priorities

Complications

The data were collected from 28 respondents with multiple insights from some respondents. 52 insights were received concerning whether they know someone with preventable complications associated with pregnancy. 19 (37%) of the respondents identified death and miscarriage; 10 (19%) pre-eclampsia, eclampsia, or diabetes; 10 (19%) infection; 4 (7.5%) pre-term or post-term labour; 4 (7.5%) anxiety or depression; 2 (4%) medical non-compliance; 1 (2%) domestic violence; 1 (2%) caesarean delivery; and 1 (2%) maternal nutrition. In addition, a respondent highlighted the conflict: “I witnessed many of my friends lose their lives while trying to give birth in the bushes; some bled, and there was nothing to help stop or replace the blood”. Further, at a household level, one respondent reported, “Complications occur when the pregnant women don't follow medical health care or feed well or rest well or due to domestic violence”, articulating a deeply concerning sensitive area. The findings reflect data from WHO, which show that pre-eclampsia and eclampsia, infection, and bleeding are among

the leading causes of maternal death in the country (WHO, 2016) while highlighting the need for targeted interventions to address preventable complications associated with pregnancy in South West Cameroon.

Figure 2. Have you or has anyone you've known experienced complications?

Experience of complications

The data also indicate that the high rate of complications and maternal mortality in the region may be attributed to the added stress and trauma caused by displacement and conflict. From 35 respondents, 29 (83%) knew someone who had experienced complications associated with pregnancy, and the testimonials received reflect the impact of displacement, conflict, and loss on maternal health. This highlights the need for interventions that address not only the physical but also the psychosocial needs of pregnant women in the affected areas.

“I get up every day and go to the form not knowing if we are going to come back or sleep there because of gun shots.”

Respondent describing what a typical day is like in their community.

Access to Antenatal Services

The data collected showed a lack of consistent attendance. Of 17 responses received, 7 (41%) reported monthly visits, 4 (24%) had 1 to 6 visits in total, 4 (24%) more than once a month, 1 (5.5%) zero visits or attended in the bush, and 1 (5.5%) not often. The reasons for non-attendance included security issues, distance to the nearest hospital, financial reasons, and prioritising safety during periods of crisis. This highlights the challenges and barriers that women in the region face in accessing maternal health care and the need for interventions such as mobile clinics or financial assistance to address these barriers. In response to why they were unable to access antenatal services, one participant said, “Because, we considered our lives first. Since there is a serious crisis going on between the government and the separatist groups.”

“Because, we considered our lives first. Since there is a serious crisis going on between the government and the separatist groups.”

Respondent on why they were unable to access antenatal services.

Knowledge of Maternal Health Needs

The survey revealed that respondents believe that women require various forms of care during pregnancy. Of 33 responses, 8 (24%) emphasised the need for better access to quality healthcare, 7 (21%) stressed the importance of personalised care visits and follow-up care, 6 (19%) highlighted the need for free medication, and 6 (17%) focused on care from family. Other health priorities mentioned include “less hard labour responsibilities, support from husbands”, ‘free healthcare’, and ‘more TBAs’ (n=3, 10%, n=2, 7%, and n=1, 2%, respectively).

“Complications occur when the pregnant women doesn't follow medical health care or feed well or rest well or due to domestic violence.”

Respondent describing why complications associated with pregnancy occur in their community.

Improvements Desired by the Community

When asked about areas in which maternal health support could be improved, the community primarily focused on better facilities and accessible health services. From 36 respondents, a total of 66 insights was received. 21 (34%) indicated the need for better facilities, general infrastructure, and medical equipment, while 20 (32%) emphasised the need for more accessible health services and centres. In addition, 9 (14.5%) highlighted the importance of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH), 5 (14.5%) emphasised the need for personnel training, and 3 (5%) mentioned family planning. The qualitative data

gives us a deeper understanding of these needs, with respondents mentioning better job opportunities to afford hospital care and money to purchase baby supplies, as well as the need for better hospitals and access to water.

4.3 Health-Seeking Behaviour

When asked about seeking medical care, 44 insights were received from 36 respondents. 27 (61%) reported seeking medical care, 3 (7%) rarely sought care, 3 (7%) did so during pregnancy. 9 (20%) cited reasons such as lack of access to doctors, distance to hospitals, financial constraints, and insecurity during the crisis which prevented them from seeking healthcare. 1 (2.5%) relied on traditional medicine and 1 (2.5%) said they rarely get sick. These results highlight the challenges and barriers to accessing medical care in South West Cameroon.

4.4 Role of Formal Health Services

Satisfaction with Health Services

Of 37 classified responses on the level of satisfaction with maternal health services in the community, 3 (8%) were very dissatisfied, 17 (46%) dissatisfied, 4 (11%) unsure, 7 (19%) satisfied, and 6 (16%) very satisfied. However, there is potential for bias, as respondents may fear being openly critical or aligning with government views. The open-ended follow-up question provided 45 insights [some providing more than one insight] on why people were dissatisfied or satisfied. It revealed higher dissatisfaction levels, with only 24.5% indicating satisfaction or neutrality. 55.5% mentioned cost, distance, or lack of resources; 13% lack of trained personnel; 4% inconsistency; and 2% poor communication/neglect. Examples of unprocessed data include “Dissatisfied with lack of qualified personnel for maternal care” and “No modern equipment for population”.

“Dissatisfied with lack of qualified personnel for maternal care”
 Respondents explanation on why they’re dissatisfied with health services.

Figure 3. Are you satisfied with the health services available to support maternal healthcare in your community?

Satisfaction with Health Workers

Of 37 classified responses on the level of satisfaction with healthcare workers supporting maternal health, 1 (2.5%) were very dissatisfied, 11 (30%) dissatisfied, 3 (8%) unsure, 15 (40.5%) satisfied, and 7 (19%) very satisfied.

In the open-ended follow-up question on why participants are satisfied or dissatisfied, of the 36 responses, those who answered expressed a lower satisfaction levels. 14 (39%) indicated satisfaction or neutrality, 12 (33%) cited lack of

resources, 5 (14%) lack of trained personnel, and 5 (14%) poor communication/neglect. Examples of unprocessed data include “Satisfied with services but insufficient resources” and “Not available during crisis”.

“Satisfied with services but insufficient resources”
 Respondent insight on why they were dissatisfied with health workers.

Figure 4. Are you satisfied with the healthcare workers supporting maternal health in your community?

Health Service Provision

Before the conflict, MME had 10 health facilities serving a population of 25,000, but 9 have since closed due to the conflict. The remaining public facility exists as 90% of pre-existing services have closed. The national government is exploring a health insurance system for Universal Healthcare Coverage, however talks are ongoing. Public sector hospitals are nationally run and paid for by the state, but most healthcare facilities require payment out of pocket (Dr Eko, 2023).

Consultation for Maternal Health Advice

When asked about who women consult for maternal health advice, 24 (66%) of 36 respondents cited health professionals, 9 (25%) local women with lived experience, and 3 (9%) family members. The unprocessed data provided contextual understanding of why women seek different services. For example, “Most women I know go to the hospital whereas, some few who cannot afford or are forced into the interior to consult local and experienced birth attendants.” and, “They go to the hospital. But because of the crisis and the fact that most of the women gave birth in the bushes, they were attended to by women in the community.”

4.5 Role of Informal Health Services

Preference of Health Services

In terms of health service preferences during pregnancy and childbirth, of 33 respondents, 22 (67%) preferred hospitals, while 11 (33%) preferred TBAs.

Figure 5. Do people in your community prefer Traditional birth attendants or hospitals?

Why Women choose TBAs

A follow-up question was asked to gain a deeper understanding of why some women choose TBAs. 32 respondents provided multiple answers; thus, 38 insights were obtained. 16 (42%) of the respondents cited cost as the primary reason, 11 (37%) cited access/conditions/situation, 4 (11%) cited culture/language, 2 (5%) cited trust/connection, and 2 (5%) cited politeness/patience. A respondent stated, "Because it is free, and you don't stress to look for money to go to the hospital," while another said, "They prefer TBAs as it's cheaper and accessible even though it's risky."

Figure 6. Do you think that TBAs would benefit from training with professional medical practitioners?

"They prefer TBAs as it's cheaper and accessible even though it's risky."

Respondent on why women choose TBAs

Training TBAs

The community was asked about their views on TBAs and whether they thought they would benefit from training with professional medical practitioners. 31 (89%) of 35 respondents agreed, with one respondent stating, "Yes, they could because in the absence of professional medical practitioners, most women turn to TBAs," and another respondent stating, "Very well because they already have the zeal and gift, with the education they will do it marvellously."

"It's always a 50/50 chance, as getting medical attendance is costly and inaccessible"

Respondent explaining the role TBAs play in the community.

Description of TBAs

When asked to describe the role TBAs play in the community, the responses emphasised the short-term need for training while the Anglophone crisis is ongoing, and the difficulties in rebuilding the health systems. One respondent said, "It's always a 50/50 chance, as getting medical attendance is costly and inaccessible," while another respondent said, "To me, these women need to be encouraged so that they can assist in areas or situations where a woman needs help in their homes."

“The desire to help people suffering because of inaccessibility to healthcare”

Respondent on what motivates people in their community to volunteer and support health initiatives

Payment to TBAs

In terms of payment for TBAs, the rates varied. When asked about how much TBAs charge per visit, 12 (46%) of 26 respondents said that TBAs are free or receive a volunteer token or gift, 7 (27%) said that they charge 1,000 FCA, 1 (3.5%) said 5,000 FCA, and 1 (3.5%) said 10,000 FCA. Additionally, 2 (8%) indicated that drugs are paid for, while the remaining 3 (12%) said the price varies. Note that where the respondents stated, ‘free’ or ‘gift’, this may mask the reality. There are examples where people have had to put up their homes as equity to have access to care, hoping to pay over a period of time. Thus, the lack of free medical facilities and provisions provided via informal markets compounds the pre-existing debt burden (Dr Eko, 2023).

“The love to help and assist others, motivates people to come support us in our community.”

Respondent on what motivates people in their community to volunteer and support health initiatives

4.6 Actors

Local Actors

28 responses were collected on the respondents’ knowledge and experience of international and local organisations working in their region.

The respondents provided 21 insights into these organisations. 10 (48%) mentioned UN Agencies, 7 (33%) mentioned Médecins Sans Frontières (MSF), 3 (14%) mentioned Zoe Health Foundation, and 1 (5%) highlighted Reachout Cameroon.

Twenty insights were obtained on the impressions of these NGOs: 7 (35%) expressed support, 7 (35%) reported receiving medical care for women and children, 4 (20%) received food assistance, and 2 (10%) received help with medical bills and funding for start-ups.

It should be noted that the high proportion of respondents mentioning UN Agencies may reflect a general recognition of NGOs and may not accurately reflect the presence of UN Agencies in the field.

Welisane Mokwe Nkeng and Dr Eko advised on the role these actors play in South West Cameroon:

- **The Ministry of Health** is considered a high-interest stakeholder, with a focus on national and regional health. The aim of meetings led by the Welisane Foundation with the Ministry of Health is to obtain real-time information about the local situation.
- **Lukmef**, is a Cameroonian NGO known for its local knowledge of the humanitarian context and need, can provide second-hand information on the challenges faced in the region.
- **Reachout Cameroon** provides information similar to Lukmef, with a focus on local knowledge.
- **United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA)** has a limited role in supporting TBAs, with a focus on maternal health. They provide training for healthcare workers, emergency obstetric care commodities, and funding for medical equipment, but are not physically present in the field.
- **MSF** has fieldwork experience and can provide first-hand information on the situation. They support healthcare provision through community health workers and empower local health facilities by referring patients to them. When working in MME, MSF worked in partnership with the Ministry of Health, regional health care workers, and UNFPA.

Figure 7. Map of actors operating in South West Cameroon in 2022

It is worth noting that since the respondents were asked in 2022, the MSF have left the region; thus, Dr Eko advises that the need for the organisation is greater today. To get a sense of the void potentially left, several respondents mentioned

MSF and the services they've provided, including one who advised: "Organisations such as MSF helped a lot in our community medically assisting bills and a quick response to local people."

4.8 Communicating Health Messages

Respondents were asked about the best way to disseminate health information within their community. 31 categorised responses revealed that a mix of digital and analogue methods was preferred, with a total of 62 insights from the respondents. 13 (24%) preferred the use of Social Media or SMS; 9 (16%) favoured town criers or quarter heads; 9 (16%) advised church announcements; 8 (15%) said radio, TV, or newspaper; 8 (15%) said health centres or healthcare workers; 4 (7%) suggested house-to-house visits or word of mouth; and 4 (7%) preferred the health ministry or NGOs.

“Through church announcements and traditional communicators or small Christian community meetings.”

Respondent concerning how best to get a message concerning health around their community.

5. Limitations and strengths

Limitations

The sample size was limited to 38 respondents due to limited time, resources, and sensitivity of the subject matter in an unstable environment with ongoing violence. Descriptive statistical analysis methods were used for this report, given the sample size, and there were concerns of respondent bias and underreporting of the situation, including fear of openly expressing how they 'really' feel. Another limitation is since the research was conducted, MSF were asked by the Government to leave MME due to a disagreement concerning providing emergency medical care to separatists, which means that needs have changed, and most likely been heightened due to their absence (Dr Eko, 2023).

Strengths

To our knowledge, this is the first survey conducted in South West Cameroon using a lay epidemiology approach to work directly with community members and gain valuable insights for future research and health initiatives in this field. “Lay epidemiology” was demonstrated through a community-led, grassroots, and informed approach. The study was conducted through building trusted relationships between Public Health Pathways and the Welisane Foundation. There was collaborative analysis between specialist advisors and teams, benefiting from diverse and high-level technical input and in-depth local insights. Data reflect a rigorous and well-considered approach to analysis.

5. Discussion

Three Delays Model

The Three Delays Model informed the survey design and findings in MME, which provide a deeper insight into the barriers to maternal health at the household, community and health system level from delays in decision-making, reaching health facilities, and receiving care.

Delay to take a decision: Financial constraints, exacerbated by the Anglophone Crisis, were identified as the primary reason for delays in decision-making. Respondents emphasised their limited financial means, which affected their ability to seek antenatal services, medical care, and led to reliance on TBAs. Additionally, most healthcare facilities require out-of-pocket payment, further complicating access to medical care.

Delay to reach health facilities: The conflict has also directly impacted the ability to receive care, as respondents reported giving birth in the bushes and facing complications during pregnancy. The ongoing conflict has led to the closure of several

health facilities making them more difficult to access. In addition, since MSF recently left MME in late 2022, it has further hampered the community's ability to reach health facilities.

Delay to receive care: Due to limited health facilities and closure, the lack of trained midwives and medical personnel, lack of drugs, and equipment, the local community in MME face several challenges in receiving maternal healthcare. The survey demonstrated the lack of access to receive consistent maternal healthcare within the community.

“To me they really cannot take care of more complicated cases and so refer people to big hospitals.”

Respondent on why they are not satisfied with the health services available.

Prior to this survey, the main problems to address in the South-West region were:

- **Medical:** cases of haemorrhaging and infection for births occurring in the community.
- **Social:** safety concerns, lack of money, and living in bushes.
- **Structural:** closure of health services and lack of staff and resources.

Medical, social, and structural reasons figure heavily in the data gathered and shed light on the structural reasons for the challenges faced in MME. Malaria was identified as a significant medical challenge, with infectious diseases threatening maternal, fetal, infant health, and being associated with anaemia, stillbirth, low birth weight, and maternal and fetal death ([Bauserman, M. et Al, 2019](#)). Social challenges include the economic toll of the conflict, leading to job loss, poverty, and decreased access to healthcare. Structural challenges include the closure of health facilities, safety concerns, and a lack of staff and resources.

In conclusion, through the Three Delays Model, the impact of the ongoing conflict on maternal health in MME includes the community's ability to make a decision, economic prospects, and capacity to reach healthcare facilities owing to the difficulty of knowing when violence may escalate or deescalate, and receive healthcare with the lack of trained personnel.

6. Analysis

Findings in other studies in Cameroon identified several factors that contributed to maternal mortality (as summarised in Figure 1). **Health system factors** that affected outcomes were accessibility to clinics, lack of midwife training, lack of trust in existing interventions, and lack of holistic health programs. The results found early marriage, customary norms and religion, traditional birthing beliefs, and a strong kinship hierarchy and structure to be **socio-cultural factors** contributing to this situation. **Relationship factors** such as a lack of peer to peer support and family support, and low trust in health professionals as well as **individual factors** such as poverty, illiteracy, pre-existing health conditions and dependency on other decision-makers contributed to high maternal mortality elsewhere in Cameroon. All these factors affect prenatal, delivery, and post-natal care as a result of delayed seeking of, accessing (or reach) of, and receiving care.

OUR BACKGROUND RESEARCH INSIGHTS

Figure 8. Factors contributing to high maternal mortality in Cameroon based on existing published research

It was hypothesised that, in South West Cameroon, maternal mortality in conflict areas may have similar and also different and unique **seek-reach-receive** issues that require a tailored intervention to better suit the context. Using the Three Delays Model to design the survey and analyse data, the enablers or barriers respondents faced in seeking, reaching, and receiving maternal care were scrutinized.

The study found that *seeking care* was not impacted by sociocultural factors such as customary norms, taboos, or birthing beliefs. In fact, the majority of respondents, 67%, preferred biomedical care as opposed to 33%, who preferred TBAs. Strong kinship hierarchy did not deter women from seeking, accessing, or receiving care. Instead, in circumstances where it was not possible to access hospitals, kinship ties enabled women to receive some care from “women who have experience” or “elder women”.

Individual factors such as decision-making power, pre-existing health conditions, and illiteracy did not delay seeking, reaching, or receiving care. Although poverty and financial reasons were frequently stated in answers to multiple questions (refer to section ‘Delay in seeking care’) and 73% of respondents who provided income information earned less than CFA 169,012 per month (US \$269; the amount required to live reasonably in rural Cameroon ([Anker Reference Values, 2022](#)), not all of them cited financial issues as a cause of delayed *seeking* of care during pregnancy. That said, 33% of respondents *preferred* TBAs over hospitals.

The major delays in accessing or reaching healthcare services were due to health system factors. Care during labour was frequently impeded, as most hospitals were closed due to the conflict. Many women reported giving birth in the bushes or at home as a result. Antenatal care attendance varied, and reported reasons for this (when provided) were predominantly due to inaccessibility or closed clinics due to the crisis. Lack of resources and trained personnel were contributing factors to inadequate care at clinics and closures.

Lack of resources and trained personnel were contributing factors to inadequate care at clinics and closures.

Relationship factors did not prevent women from seeking or receiving care except in a few cases where preference for TBAs was indicated due to better emotional support or care. Some women did not trust the health system and showed they were dissatisfied with the level of care shown by health workers although it did not alter their preference for biomedical care. Where mentioned, dissatisfaction with hospital services and workers did not necessarily directly translate to a preference for TBAs or a preference to seek other means of maternal care. This indicates an overall preference for biomedical interventions but an inability to access them due to the absence of staff or closed clinics and some financial barriers. Peer-to-peer support is very high in this context during labour, as there is a reliance on elderly or experienced women in the absence of biomedical care. Whether this level of peer-to-peer support exists for antenatal care is unclear. Thus peer-to-

peer support is an enabler of better care in the absence of biomedical care in this context. No barriers to seeking care as a result of family beliefs or reservations were identified in the study. Moreover, through training TBAs, opportunities exist to link and strengthen existing healthcare services.

From the above, it is clear that interventions that can strengthen or enable access to biomedical care will not face barriers from the local community. They are willing to take up biomedical care more readily than traditional care, and only prefer traditional forms of care when hospitals are closed, staff are unavailable, or services are unaffordable. TBAs are respected and valued for their empathy and affordability but are not preferred due to the risk involved due to lack of equipment in cases of complications, which confirms that there is an opportunity to train TBAs to counter the identified lack of staff in hospitals to provide better and timely care outside hospital settings. The dissatisfaction in health workers attitudes towards patients and the appreciation of emotional support by TBAs indicates that any training intervention should also focus on delivering care empathetically and with emotional support. The research also confirms that currently, most women are depending on women in the community to assist during delivery and that this frequently happens in the bush, not in a clean setting. It will therefore be beneficial to provide training to these women and equip them with basic kits to minimise post-partum infections and bleeding, both of which contribute greatly to Cameroon’s high maternal mortality rate.

The dissatisfaction in health workers attitudes towards patients and the appreciation of emotional support by TBAs indicates that any training intervention should also focus on delivering care empathetically and with emotional support.

As there were no family or kinship structures or other decision-makers contributing to barriers to seeking or accessing care, interventions do not need to include ‘permission’ from authoritative family members or community ‘gatekeepers’.

The survey responses also confirmed that Malaria is the most pressing health concern. Additionally, as it can severely affect maternal health outcomes and as there is such varied antenatal monitoring and attendance, it is vital that interventions address antenatal care with malarial prophylaxis as a focal point.

The results on health communications indicate that the majority receive health information via digital means (social media) followed by the church (predominantly Christian and Catholic faith) as well as radio. Thus, one possibility is to tailor the training delivery using telecommunications or radio. Antenatal self-monitoring could be delivered through mobile technology like FamilyConnect and by creating village health teams leveraging ‘elder’ or ‘experienced women’. Tele-training can also be conducted to train TBAs and also provide training to elderly or experienced women in the community for using emergency delivery kits for safer, cleaner deliveries outside of a hospital setting. While network or telecommunication breakdowns during the conflict may be a problem, initiatives such as the Emergency Telecommunications Cluster (ETC) could be partnered with to deliver telecommunication-based interventions. Physical training provision could also be held at the Church, as this seems to be a central point for information in the community.

7. Recommendations for the project

The survey shows that the community prefers hospitals over TBAs and supports training for TBAs. It is understood that training TBAs does not overcome the need for improved access to quality maternal health facilities. However, the conflict is ongoing and between periods of escalated violence and de-escalated violence. Further, it is difficult to extrapolate from such a small sample. Nonetheless, until there is stability, the key recommendation is that training TBAs in midwifery is beneficial to increase the capacity of the community to support pregnant women and births, improve links with healthcare facilities, and increase trust through greater integration into the healthcare system.

Objectives

General objective: To improve maternal care and skilled birth attendance to reduce maternal mortality in MME.

Specific objectives to:

- Increase the number of antenatal care visits,
- Increase the number of skilled attended births, and
- Train staff to create an environment of trust between TBAs, the community, and healthcare providers and personnel.

Impact

The expected impact of the proposed project is to bridge the gap between untrained TBAs and trained midwives by building a continuum of care through increased human resources, an effective referral system, and training. The three delays are expected to be prevented via sustained localised access to trained assistance within the community to provide basic preventative antenatal care and identify early warning signals along with an effective early referral system that flags when a TBA should refer mothers to a nurse. Targeting the three delays via this impact model could contribute to reducing maternal mortality in South West Cameroon (see Figure 9).

Figure 9. Expected impact of the SMiLES project

Project plan

The overriding aims of the project are safer birthing and the reduction in maternal mortality in emergency settings. To achieve this, SMiLES has two overlapping phases that combine a training course and a kit source and supply phase (see Figure 10 for further details).

The survey data has informed the SMiLES project plan, which includes a training phase, starting with a recruitment drive for trainers and respondents, TBAs and experienced women in the community, and midwives and nurses from clinics to create an antenatal and postpartum continuum of care with a foundation for training. The training will include and is not limited to antenatal services [including Malaria intermittent preventive treatment (IPT)], clean delivery, and a postpartum care course. Further, a maternal care network will be set up via social media and telecoms to support all those involved. The kit course and supply phase will involve planning supply chain logistics, human resources for logistics coordination (with malaria IPT integrated), and procurement that leads to sustained antenatal and safe delivery kits.

In addition, a monitoring and evaluation plan will be created and executed to report and refine the implementation to ensure transparency, better performance, and learn lessons for future programs.

Next steps

Public Health Pathways supported The Welisane Foundation with research, data analysis, and report writing. From October 2023 Public Health Pathways stepped down from SMiLES, having introduced The Welisane Foundation to senior London-based academics with international maternal health expertise to explore the next steps.

Figure 10. Draft Theory of Change for the SMILES project

8. Conclusion

The locally led and informed data collection in this study demonstrates the key role 'lay epidemiology' can play in low-income settings to understand and co-develop interventions that strengthen healthcare systems. As per insights from local experts, SMILES is the first project in the South West region aiming to empower TBAs. To date, there have been limited attempts to train and re-skill them. Indeed, some see them as part of the problem, but it must be understood that most delays in treatment are due to the state of the healthcare system. Even though TBAs provide an unofficial service, they are crucial in empowering healthcare facilities and can play a vital role in strengthening maternal healthcare services. In addition, the present conflict is in an unpredictable phase, and fighting may return. Thus, this proposed pilot aims to first support TBAs and the local population, and thereafter, build community resilience should the conflict re-escalate. At the same time, the SMILES project is unique because it directly involves the communities in order to develop their capabilities and skills to strengthen their capacity for providing health services in a conflict zone.

Before the survey, the long-term goal of the SMILES project was to provide safe delivery kits and design community training programs in the use of these kits to enable women in communities to self-administer treatment or assist mothers during delivery to reduce the associated risk of delivery outside a health facility. This aim remains. However, once stability returns, a secondary aim will be to enable former TBAs to contribute further to their communities. This can act as a precedent to transform communities in emergency settings, where the pilot aims to demonstrate how a future can be built using the knowledge within communities to open paths to provide advanced midwifery training, allowing communities to develop free and accessible professional maternal health services.

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